

Uplifting research software tools at Amsterdam UMC: Activity report

Bauke van der Velde¹

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Executive summary

We evaluated three Amsterdam UMC research software tools (BIOMERO², ENCORE³, and FlexRL⁴) to assess their software-management practices using the ELIXIR-STEERS Software Management Plan (SMP-KM) framework ([Suchánek et al., 2025](#)). The evaluation combined repository review, SMP completion, and developer interviews.

All three tools demonstrated strong scientific value, active development, and use of version control. Common areas for improvement included machine-readable citation metadata, archival preservation at the level of the main software artifact, testing, and licensing. While some tools already provided citation instructions or component-level Zenodo records, these practices were not implemented consistently across the primary repositories evaluated in this study.

Developers generally found the SMP process valuable for identifying blind spots and reflecting on software sustainability. However, they also highlighted opportunities to improve the framework, including adaptive question pathways, better integration with GitHub and software registries, and clearer guidance on licensing and dependencies.

¹ Research Software Management Team, Research Data Management, Research Support, Amsterdam UMC

² <https://github.com/NL-Biolmaging/BIOMERO>

³ <https://github.com/EDS-Bioinformatics-Laboratory/ENCORE>

⁴ <https://github.com/robachowyk/FlexRL>

The findings suggest that relatively small interventions, such as implementing CITATION.cff files, archiving releases, improving testing practices, and providing clearer licensing guidance, could substantially improve the discoverability, sustainability, reusability, and maintainability of research software developed at Amsterdam UMC.

Introduction

Research software is an increasingly important research output at Amsterdam UMC. It supports data analysis, reproducibility, collaboration, and reuse, but is often developed within individual projects without consistent guidance on documentation, citation, preservation, licensing, or long-term maintenance. This reflects a wider challenge in scholarly research: software is central to modern research practice, but its citation, preservation, and reuse require dedicated support and infrastructure ([Barker et al., 2022](#); [Smith, Katz & Niemeyer, 2016](#)). As part of the LDCC2-RSE deliverables, we evaluated three Amsterdam UMC research software tools to identify existing good practices, recurring gaps, and practical opportunities for support.

The case-study tools were: BIOMERO, a cloud-enabled framework for bioimage analysis; ENCORE, a toolkit for packaging reproducible research objects; and FlexRL, an R package for probabilistic linkage of patient records. For each tool, the objectives were to (1) prepare a retrospective Software Management Plan (SMP) using the ELIXIR-STEERS SMP Knowledge Model via the Data Stewardship Wizard⁵, (2) identify best practices already in place and those missing, and (3) register the tool in community registries (e.g. the Research Software Directory⁶, bio.tools⁷, and Zenodo⁸).

This report summarizes the methodology and findings of the evaluation. We first describe how the tools were selected and how the case studies were conducted. We then report common findings across the three tools, including strengths, areas for improvement, and

⁵ <https://smw.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard>

⁶ <https://research-software-directory.org>

⁷ <https://bio.tools>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org>

feedback on the SMP framework. Finally, we discuss how the findings can inform follow-up actions for the individual projects, institutional research software support, and the SMP framework itself.

Methods

Tool selection

In selecting tools for the case studies, we drew from a list containing 282 git repositories that could be associated with Amsterdam UMC. These repositories were collected via recommendations of colleagues, incoming service requests, local meetups, the FAIR Tools Framework⁹ project, search engine queries, and association with our centrally governed GitHub organization at <https://github.com/AmsterdamUMC>.

We screened the 282 repositories for software in scope, defined as repositories containing research software tools (see [Gruenpeter et al., 2021](#); [Psomopoulos, 2025](#)) that were actively developed by employees at Amsterdam UMC. An initial LLM-assisted screening reduced the set to 45 candidate repositories, which we next manually assessed to yield 13 repositories in scope. We reached out to maintainers of three repositories, selected to cover a diverse range of research purposes. All took part in the case studies upon our request.

Case study procedure

The evaluation followed a three-phase workflow.

- In Phase A (Screening), we independently reviewed each tool's code repository, documentation, and publications, completing an initial version of the ELIXIR-STEERS SMP via the DS Wizard, drawing general guidance from the Practical Guide to SMPs ([Martinez-Ortiz et al., 2023](#)), and reporting our findings.

⁹ <https://tdcc.nl/projects/tdcc-lsh-project-initiatives/#fair-tool>

- In Phase B (Interview), we met with the primary developer(s) of each tool to discuss unresolved questions and confirm details about development practices, licensing, and future plans. Meeting notes and agreed action items were recorded.
- In Phase C (Wrap-up), all findings were consolidated. Missing information was obtained from developers if needed, suggestions were prioritized, and tasks were allocated for follow-up (such as registry entries, additional documentation, or SMP tool enhancements).

Software Management Plan

The ELIXIR-STEERS SMP Knowledge Model (SMP-KM), implemented via the DS Wizard, guides documentation of research software practices across governance, funding, team roles, documentation, testing, community engagement, and sustainability. We applied the SMP retrospectively to evaluate existing practices and identify areas for improvement. The goal was to understand current software-management practices rather than prescribe new workflows.

Results

Best practices

Each of the three tools is scientifically valuable (e.g., [Luik et al., 2026](#); [Robach et al., 2025](#); [van Kampen et al., 2024](#)) and actively maintained, but their software-management maturity varied. Across the reports, the strongest recurring elements were clear purpose, usable documentation, and at least some form of versioning or citation support. All three tools had adopted version control and maintained active codebases, and all had invested in some form of user-facing documentation. Yet maturity diverged markedly when we looked beyond these basics.

The case studies also revealed several strong practices that can serve as examples for other projects. These included deliberate minimisation of dependencies, structured API documentation, semantic versioning, release notes, user-facing tutorials, machine-

readable citation support within R, and component-level automated testing. This suggests that research software at Amsterdam UMC is not starting from zero. Rather, many projects already apply good practices locally, but need support to make these practices more consistent, visible, and sustainable across the full software artifact.

Table 1. Software-management practice maturity across the three case-study tools

Practice	Cross-case finding
Version control	Present across all tools
User-facing documentation	Present in some form across all tools, but maturity varied
Developer onboarding documentation	Limited or absent across tools
Machine-readable citation metadata	Incomplete or inconsistent across primary repositories
Zenodo archival preservation	Present for some components, but not consistently for main software artifacts
RSD / bio.tools registration	Incomplete at screening, completed as part of the project
Automated testing / CI	Present for some components, but inconsistent across tools
Licensing clarity	Inconsistent across all tools

Table 1 summarizes the main cross-case patterns. The strongest recurring practices were version control, active development, and some form of user-facing documentation. The most common areas for improvement concerned consistency across the main software artifact: machine-readable citation metadata, archival preservation, registry entries, automated testing, developer onboarding, and licensing clarity. As a direct outcome of this study, all three tools were, when possible without any naming confusions, registered in the Research Software Directory and bio.tools, improving their discoverability within the research software ecosystem.

Documentation

All three tools had some form of user-facing documentation, but its maturity and usability varied. Developer onboarding documentation was more limited across the case studies. Clear separation between user and developer documentation emerged as a gap, particularly for tools with modular codebases where new contributors would need to understand internal architecture. None of the tools had contribution guidelines (such as CONTRIBUTING.md files) that would signal to potential contributors how to get involved or what the development workflow looks like. This absence, while not critical for mature tools with stable maintainer teams, becomes a sustainability risk as projects age or maintainers change.

Testing and continuous integration

Testing practices varied not only in maturity, but also in form. One project had automated tests and continuous integration at component level, but not for the full platform. Another relied mainly on structured manual evaluation rounds, while the third used function examples that served as informal manual tests. This suggests that testing should not be treated as a binary requirement. For research software projects, a useful next step is often to formalize existing manual or example-based checks into lightweight automated tests and run these through continuous integration. Even a small test suite, focused on core functionality, would help catch regressions and increase confidence in future releases without requiring major refactoring.

Governance

Beyond documentation and testing, the case studies highlighted governance risks around repository stewardship. These included repositories under personal accounts, unclear backup maintainership, and limited structured tracking of software identifiers, registry entries, and support status.

Multi-component software

A recurring challenge was that several tools were better understood as software ecosystems rather than single software artifacts. NL-BIOMERO consists of a platform,

library, importer, web plugin, Docker deployment setup, and external service integrations. ENCORE similarly consists of several related components, including the sFSS template, FSS Navigator, and ENCORE_AUTOMATION, each with its own role, license, and archival record. This complicated SMP questions about citation, dependencies, testing, licensing, and preservation, because answers differed across components. Future SMP tooling should better support multi-component projects by allowing component-level answers that can be summarized at project level.

Licensing

Licensing emerged as a recurring area of uncertainty across the three tools. Each tool included some form of licensing information, but the scope of these licenses was not always clear. In particular, it was sometimes unclear which license applied to executable code, documentation, templates, or supporting materials.

The issue was especially visible in multi-component projects, where different repositories or components used different licenses. Creative Commons licenses were also encountered in software contexts. While these may be appropriate for documentation or templates, they are generally not designed for executable code and should be used deliberately.

The case studies also raised questions about intellectual property ownership for software developed during employment. This was not assessed as a legal question, but it does point to a need for clearer institutional guidance.

Researchers would benefit from practical support on choosing software-appropriate licenses, expressing licenses in SPDX compatible formats¹⁰, separating code and documentation licenses where needed, and knowing when to seek institutional advice. Clarifying these issues early could reduce ambiguity and help developers make informed decisions about reuse, redistribution, and commercial use.

¹⁰ <https://spdx.org/licenses/>

Feedback on Software Management Plan

Comprehensiveness

Participants found the SMP questions on funding, contributors, and registration useful for uncovering blind spots. For example, several developers had not formally registered their tools in software directories until prompted by the SMP questions, and the structured questions about contributor roles helped clarify who was responsible for maintenance and support. They also appreciated distinctions between documentation types (user vs. developer docs), which prompted reflection on gaps in their documentation strategy. Overall, the SMP template functioned as a useful checklist: it didn't ask developers to change practice, but it helped them see what they were already doing well and where attention was needed.

Usability and adaptability

However, some questions were deemed burdensome or context-sensitive, and developers expressed frustration with a one-size-fits-all approach. A small research tool in early stages has different needs than a mature infrastructure project with dozens of contributors, yet the SMP template presented the same questions to both. Suggestions included adding an initial "intake" phase to gauge project size, scope, and maturity level, which could then branch to simpler or more detailed question tracks accordingly. Adaptive or branching questions (for example, asking detailed dependency questions only if a project has multiple sub-modules, or detailed team-management questions only if there are multiple developers) would reduce question fatigue without sacrificing comprehensiveness. We suggest a "good-enough" reference example or template answer showing what a realistic SMP looks like for a tool at their maturity level, rather than an idealized exemplar.

Integration and automation

A major usability barrier was redundancy: developers were asked to provide information (license, contributors, code coverage) that already existed in GitHub or in their Zenodo records or bio.tools entries. We suggest an SMP tool that fetches this information directly

from GitHub APIs, reducing manual data entry and keeping answers synchronized with the actual project state. Similarly, integration or export options with registries (Zenodo, bio.tools, Research Software Directory) would avoid re-entering metadata. An exportable, human-readable report was highlighted as a particularly useful feature, allowing developers to generate a snapshot of their SMP for institutional records, funder reports, or team documentation without manually copying and pasting from the web interface.

Clarity on contentious topics

The SMP should also clarify license implications and provide stronger guidance on common misconceptions. For instance, the tool should warn developers that CC licenses (e.g., CC BY-NC-SA) are inappropriate for software code, or flag when license choices conflict with institutional IP policies. Similarly, the SMP should better define dependency scope (distinguishing core dependencies from optional or development-only dependencies), particularly for modular or containerized projects where Docker or conda environments obscure the underlying dependency tree. Developers expressed uncertainty about what counted as a "dependency" and how to report it accurately, suggesting the template needs clearer definitions or examples.

Discussion

The structured case-study process proved useful because it combined three perspectives: repository review, hands-on assessment, and direct conversation with developers. Together, these steps revealed issues that would not have been visible from repository metadata alone. The findings were not primarily tool-specific failures, but recurring patterns in how research software is developed, documented, preserved, and governed in an academic setting.

A central finding is that many good practices are already present, but often unevenly or only within parts of a software ecosystem. Version control, user-facing documentation, release practices, citation instructions, and testing were all present in some form across

the case studies. However, these practices were not always implemented consistently at the level of the main software artifact. This was especially clear for multi-component projects, where repositories, licenses, documentation, tests, and archival records differed between components. Supporting research software therefore requires more than checking whether a practice is present or absent. It requires helping developers make existing practices explicit, consistent, and sustainable across the full project.

The SMP framework was valuable in this context as a diagnostic tool. It helped structure the evaluation and prompted useful reflection on topics such as contributors, funding, documentation, registration, testing, and licensing. At the same time, the case studies show that SMPs need to balance completeness with usability. A single, detailed questionnaire is useful for retrospective assessment of mature software but may be too demanding for early-stage projects or small tools maintained by one or two researchers. A tiered approach, supported by automated metadata retrieval and clearer examples, would make the SMP more useful as practical guidance rather than only as an audit instrument.

These findings point to a broader role for institutional research software support. Many of the recommended improvements are relatively small, such as adding machine-readable citation metadata, archiving releases, improving registry entries, documenting contribution workflows, or formalizing existing manual tests. Their impact, however, is potentially large because they improve discoverability, continuity, reuse, and maintainability. The case studies therefore suggest that Amsterdam UMC can strengthen research software not only through individual project support, but also through reusable guidance, shared procedures, and clearer institutional expectations.

Implications and next steps

The case studies led to several concrete follow-up actions. At project level, we will support developers in adding machine-readable citation metadata, archiving software releases, improving registry entries, and formalizing existing testing and documentation

practices where needed. Several registry actions have already been completed as part of the case-study workflow.

At institutional level, the findings will be used to develop practical guidance for researchers developing software at Amsterdam UMC. This includes guidance on CITATION.cff files, Zenodo release archiving, software registration, contributor documentation, and lightweight testing practices. Licensing support should receive particular attention, including guidance on software-appropriate licenses, mixed licensing in multi-component projects, and situations where institutional advice is needed.

The feedback on the SMP framework has also been shared with the ELIXIR-STEERS SMP-KM developers. Key recommendations include tiered question pathways, better integration with GitHub and software registries, clearer examples, and more explicit guidance on licensing and dependency scope. Together, these next steps should make research software support more practical, less burdensome, and easier to apply early in the software lifecycle.

Limitations

This report is based on three case studies from Amsterdam UMC. The tools were selected partly because their maintainers were willing to participate, which may have resulted in a sample of projects whose developers were already relatively engaged with documentation, sustainability, or software quality. The findings should therefore not be interpreted as representative of all research software developed at the institution.

The evaluation was also retrospective. We assessed repositories, documentation, publications, and developer accounts after the software had already been developed. As a result, we may have missed informal practices, earlier design decisions, or undocumented constraints that shaped the projects. In addition, the small number of tools limits the extent to which we can generalize the observed patterns beyond these cases.

At the same time, the case-study approach provided depth that would have been difficult to obtain through automated screening or surveys alone. Repository review, hands-on assessment, and conversations with developers made it possible to identify practical barriers, contextual constraints, and realistic improvement paths. The findings should therefore be read as exploratory but actionable: they do not define the full state of research software at Amsterdam UMC, but they do indicate where targeted support could have immediate value.

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